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**A STUDY ON COGNITIVE ACTIONS AND IMAGERY
DEVELOPMENT SKILL: TOWARDS A PATTERN LANGUAGE
FOR NOVICE DESIGNERS**

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ABSTRACT

The theme of this thesis is to evaluate the possibility of utilizing pattern language to assist designer's preliminary idea. According to Alexander's proposition, the concept of pattern language is to help novice architects to study design through the systematic process. This study is to investigate whether novices would have a great improvement in idea sketching toward a pattern language. The experiment in this study includes two principal parts. The first part is to find a systematizing method to generalize pattern language by inviting experts to join a design workshop to edit a series of systematic pattern language through the discussion. The pattern language is made by the picture card, containing four key elements: 1.Name, 2.Picture, 3.Question, 4.Solution, it make novice easier to learn by it. The second part is to prove pattern language could promote its picture idea and develop novices' ability through the process of studying. By dividing into the experiment group and the contrast group, the experiment group sketch toward pattern language; and the contrast group chooses the catalog method by watching a large number of pictures. We would compare and analyze the difference between these two methods through the information what video camera recorded. The result of this investigation finds that the cognitive actions in both groups are similar; it may be because the both groups are all novices. However, there is a huge diversity of the cognitive thinking way organized by the cognitive action in both groups. The novices utilizing pattern language have the continuous and systematic

cognitive thinking that consisted of the cognitive action .The thinking of the other novices on catalog method is discontinuous and inefficient. According to the evaluation of the experts' assessment, the novices utilizing pattern language is more efficient than the novice designers on catalog method.

Keywords: Pattern Language, Cognitive Action, Imagery Development.

INTRODUCTION

Sketching plays an important part in the design process. It involves concrete objects produced by designers' mind. Therefore, novice designers should emphasize how to sketch well. We conducted a design training workshop for student novice designers from NCKU Industrial Design Department, and evaluated its effect when the training is conducted through pattern language or the catalog method. Tracy Lewis(2002) said that'' a good pattern language should give designers freedom to express themselves and to tailor their solutions to the particular needs of the context where the patterns are applied [7]. We transformed the concept of pattern language into the field of industrial design, and discussed its advantage. We stressed the relationship between designers' cognitive actions when sketching and what they draw. This analysis helps us to find novices' inadequacy and improve on it.

PATTERN LANGUAGES AND CATALOG METHOD

Christopher Alexander first proposed the concept of pattern language in <A Pattern Language>. The main idea is to enable people not trained in the professional design to design their houses, streets, or towns. People always depend on a "certain language", when designing their environment, to communicate their thoughts. The contribution of Alexander is to simplify originally complex processes for ordinary people to handle with ease. In his view, it's satisfying for them to be involved in their own environment since they know most clearly what they really want, and let them design the environment that best meets their needs. This has revolutionary value. He established a reliable design process by analyzing architects' design process in quantitative terms. He also replaced talent with the reasonable training in people's impression of "design" needs. Whether it is architecture, industrial design, city planning or other area of design, the accent is on the efficiency in the method of creation to produce the architecture or product that solves problems in ways for all to see. Pattern language provides beginners with a way to design according to the values of the field of architecture. This research will try to use pattern language in the field of industrial design, and try to find out if it has true value in helping designers to establish the concepts in their minds through sketching, including trying to train them in the skill of shaping concepts. Because the language of architecture is too broad to translate into product syntax, we will make some changes in writing this research report. Originally, the way to write this is:

1. Denomination: according to our life, we denominate by noticing the special environment.
2. Picture: To show the situation in pictures,
3. Relating to the upper- pattern: The pattern related to the pattern.
4. Question: in text explain simply.
5. Recommendation of solution to problem: In text, show the solution to the problem.
6. Relating to the under- pattern: the patter related to the pattern.

Because of the complexity of architecture, the field of architecture has upper and under patterns. In the field of industrial design, only the products which are more complex belong to this kind of pattern, like vehicles. The products which are simpler medically

or modally shouldn't be concerned about divisions in these two, upper and under, patterns. In this research, the ways to write it were changed into 1. Denomination 2. Picture 3. Question 4. Solution and recommendation, as an attempt to translate architecture the product syntax process(Yi-Chuen Chang, 2003). By the way, the completed pattern language is too broad to get information from the resource. In this research, we plan to use the pattern language to help designers to share their concepts at the beginning of the process, and build a systematic pattern language process. Alexander took 10 years to use the data of pattern language to build a complete and applied theory. This required immense architecture experience and knowledge. So it's worth discussing applied and complete patterns by gaining a certain amount of data in a short time. Tracy Lewis (2002) tried to edit the pattern language on the basis of the discussion in a workshop. The research would edit the pattern language by holding a workshop. We would invite people who have experience in design- training to test and improve on the conclusion. In 1937, Osborn first introduced the method "brain storming". There are over 300 kinds of creative design process. That's why the definition of creating is always too broad. So we could combine any different methods to create a new creative method. Hoshino (1993) recommend the catalogues method in the creative process. The catalogues method works prompting associations with images. The catalogues method is an original stimulation-prompting method and is also natural. This is why we chose this to be compared with pattern language in various creative processes to research on sketch-notice and open- image ability. The other reason for choosing the catalogue method is that most students a large number of pictures to inspire their thinking. The catalogues method is used to be compared with pattern language at the stage of concept sketching in the beginner's learning process. Pattern language provides an organized and systematic way to think. The catalogues method involves the use of a large number of images by the beginners to help them establish their concepts

COGNITIVE ACTIONS

In to "What Architects See in their Design Process", Suwa and Tversky observe the designers' actions in

the design process, and they segment their noticing actions for systematic analysis. They classify the information on sketch- noticing into four kinds: 1. To describe the noticing character of elements, 2. The functional thoughts, 3. The spatial relationship, 4. Background knowledge. To conclude the noticing acts of designer's sketch established step, we also find four kinds of them: 1. Physical action, 2. Perceptual, 3. Functional action, 4. Conceptual action. We record the noticing actions of each kind and identify the differences in "amount", "how to build" and "noticing sketch"

METHOD

There are two main stages in this research. The goal of the first stage is to create a set of pattern language that suits the field of product design. We conducted a design workshop in which experts of product design to collect usable pattern languages. 6 experts were asked to join the workshop and were assigned a task. The pattern language created would be used by novice designers, and would be compared with the catalog method used by others novices in the second stage.

EXPERIMENTAL SUBJECT

We used a product composed of modeling elements in this experiment. Some functional products do not show differences in imagery development skills. Chairs are chosen as the object in this experiment because furniture is all around us in our everyday life. In product design, how to develop a product which is joyful is very important. The customer using a joyful product not only has fun but also passes a cheerful feeling to others. The novices who were asked to join this experiment were NCKU ID department freshmen. They were not studying product design but had already learnt basic skills in drawing and perspective. In order to avoid inaccuracy these students are chose since who had the same level of achievement in drawing and perspective.

THE FIRST STAGE --- HOW TO CREATE PATTERN LANGUAGE

In order to construct a set of pattern language which could be utilized in the field of industrial design, we

tried to construct the pattern language in an effective way in this research. Tracy Lewis (2002) stated in "A Community Learns Design" that the elements of pattern language are name, picture, question, and suggestion. We designed a test paper to sum up 30 pattern languages of joyful furniture based on four elements: 1. Denomination 2. Picture 3. Question 4. Solution. Then, the 30 pattern languages were classified, using the KJ method, into styles. There are 5 styles from these patterns. They are 1. conceptualization 2. modeling 3. living style 4. affection 5. dramatic change.

THE SECOND STAGE --- COMPARING WITH PATTERN LANGUAGE AND THE CATALOG METHOD

There were the experimental group and the comparison group in the second stage. The 12 novice designers of the experimental group were divided into 4 teams and were asked to design a joyful chair using pattern language. The 12 novice designers of the comparison group were divided into 4 teams and were also asked to perform the same task using the catalog method. We video-recorded how the novice designers sketched their ideas in their design process.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

According to the data from the video recording in the experiment, we classified these data to 6 kinds of cognitive actions: D-action, L-action, M-action, P-action, F-action, G-action. Physical actions refer to three main groups of actions: drawing new elements, tracing over and copying previously drawn elements on another sheet (D-actions), paying attention to previously drawn elements (L-actions), and movements on design depictions (M-actions). Perceptual actions (P-actions) refer to the mention of the visual features of elements (such as shape, size, or texture). Functional actions (F-actions) refer to the association of particular visuo-spatial features in sketches with meanings, functions or abstract concepts. Conceptual actions refer to preferential or aesthetic evaluations and the set-up of goals (G-actions). The cognitive actions of the novice designers of the experimental group and the comparison group found that the design protocol of the experimental group includes 1843 actions, while the comparison group's protocol includes 1706

actions.(Table1). The experimental group's Standard Deviation (SD) was higher than the comparison group's (73.93 > 35.70), because the experimental group's third sub-group obviously underperformed (mean value =79.67 < 153.58). A reason might be the members of this group were introvert and did not know each other well. There was little difference between the comparison group and the experiment group in the structure of the cognitive actions, according to Table2 and Table3. But during the concept development process, the sketching cognitive actions are unceasingly transformed and also have continuity. Therefore, the discussion of the continuity of the sketching cognitive actions and the thinking modes what these sketching cognitive actions constitute are valued in this research.

THE CONTINUITY OF THE SKETCHING COGNITIVE ACTIONS

There were 4 main combinations of the cognitive sketching actions that we found on the basis of video.Different combinations of the cognitive sketching actions would constitute different thinking modes.We would compare the difference in thinking mode between the comparison group and the experimental group.

1. M、L、P-action combination

This sketch-noticing process through a combination of M-action, L-action and P-action involves reading and using card images to discuss and establish concepts. This process helps our thinking with the image of language pattern.

2. D、P-action combination

This sketch- noticing process through a combination D-action and P-action helps our thinking by drawing images or making the annotations. Usually, D-action plays a more front-line role than, or an equal role as, P-action in creating the annotations or drawings.

3. M、P-action combination

The sketch-noticing process through a combination of M-action and P-action involves the use of hand-signals or body language to explain concepts and combine ways of thinking. This kind of process is usually used when someone explains some concepts to others.

4. L、P-action combination

L-action and P-action combine in this sketch-noticing process, which involves watching someone else's sketches or having further concepts. This kind of method always have similar thinking process with others.

THE DIFFERENCE OF THE THINKING MODE BETWEEN TWO GROUPS

We might discover from the Table 4 that the experimental group's M-action, L-action, and P-action combination occurred obviously more frequently than the comparison group's (122 > 41). This result shows the use of pattern language by novices helps in concept development is more than the use of the catalog method does. The D-action and P-action combination occurred slightly more frequently in the experimental group than the comparison group (31 > 28). This result shows records in the graphics or the written notes help in concept development for the experimental group more than for the comparison group. The M-action and P-action combination occurred is more frequently in the comparison group than the experimental group (18 > 9). This result shows the I movement or body language helped in concept development for the comparison group more than for the experimental group. The L-action and P-action combination occurred more frequently in the experimental group than in the comparison group (65 > 46). This result shows watching other people's sketches and discussing with others helped concept development for the experimental group more than for the comparison group.

THE EVALUATION OF IMAGERY DEVELOPMENT SKILL

7 experts were invited to score the sketches produced by the novices from the two groups in terms of the following criteria: joyful, ergonomics, aesthetic, creative, feasibility, and overall evaluation. 10 is the highest score, and 1 the lowest score. The results were examined by one-way ANOVA, the novices using the pattern language were given a higher mean value on overall evaluation than the novices using the catalog method (5.76 > 4.90, $p=0.048<0.05$)(Table5), however not any significant difference were observed on other five criterias.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the results and discussion above, the conclusions are as follows:

(1) Comparing the use of pattern language to help sketch and establish concepts with watching a large number of images in the traditional way, we could see that pattern language could help beginners think more systematically. Such efficient thinking could also bring better performance establishing concepts in a short time.

(2) In the early part of the training, we should try to develop efficient thinking, and let them practice how to establish their own thinking and present their concepts.

(3) When beginners practice design, team work could inspire variety and compellability. Also, they could judge their thinking through discussion with their partners.

(4) Although pattern language could help us to have systematically in creative thinking, to over- depend on it will limit our imagination. Try to properly use pattern language is the correct way to establish concepts.

The recommend for further research: It would be better to take into consideration the personality of

the testers when choosing people to join the test, or prepare an aptitude test to prevent deviation. That is because if the testers in the same group are friends, the result of the discussion with each other would be better.

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	Team	The amount of single novice's actions	Total
Comparison Group	1	Mean=127.00, SD =14.42	1706
	2	Mean=187.33, SD =2.52	Mean=142.17
	3	Mean=145.67, SD =38.44	SD =35.70
	4	Mean=108.67, SD =14.47	
Experimental Group	1	Mean=230.33, SD =56.00	1843
	2	Mean=190.33, SD =61.89	Mean=153.58
	3	Mean=79.67, SD =32.52	SD =73.93
	4	Mean=114.00, SD =25.12	

Table 1. The Numbers of Total Actions

	M,L,P-action combination	D,P-action combination	M,P-action combination	L,P-action combination
Comparison group	41	20	18	46
Experimental group	122	31	9	65

Table 2. The Numbers of Different Action

	Action type	People	Total	mean	SD
Comparison group	L-action	12	229	19.08	8.13
	M-action	12	364	30.33	5
	D-action	12	623	51.92	20.37
	P-action	12	430	35.83	16.38
	F-action	12	39	3.25	2.96
	G-action	12	22	1.83	2.12
Experimental group	L-action	12	295	24.58	17.04
	M-action	12	399	33.25	19.63
	D-action	12	581	48.42	22.47
	P-action	12	495	41.25	22.45
	F-action	12	42	3.5	2.39
	G-action	12	31	2.58	1.08

Table 3. The Percentage of Different Action

	Physical action				Perceptual action	Functional action	Conceptual action
	L-action	M-action	D-action	total	P-action	F-action	G-action
Comparison group	13.42%	21.34%	36.52%	71.28%	25.21%	2.29%	1.23%
Experimental group	16.01%	21.65%	31.52%	69.18%	26.86%	2.28%	1.68%

Table 4. The Numbers of Different Combination of Action

	Comparison group		Experimental group		test of homogeneity	p-value
	mean	sd	mean	sd		
joyful	5.58	1.03	5.14	1.05	0.702	0.302
ergonomics	4.76	0.76	4.65	0.88	0.852	0.774
aesthetic	5.00	1.20	4.71	0.93	0.578	0.504
creative	5.51	1.30	5.25	1.11	0.283	0.600
feasibility	5.45	0.65	5.75	0.33	0.331	0.308
Overall evaluation	4.90	0.87	5.76	1.14	0.659	0.048*

Table 5. The Evaluation Results of Two Groups